

Development of deep reinforcement learning for inverted pendulum

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a modification of the deep Q-network (DQN) in deep reinforcement learning to control the angle of the inverted pendulum (IP). The original DQN method often uses two actions related to two force states like constant negative and positive force values which apply to the cart of IP to maintain the angle between the pendulum and the Y-axis. Due to the changing of too much value of force, the IP may make some oscillation which makes the performance system could be declined. Thus, a modified DQN algorithm is developed based on neural network structure to make a range of force selections for IP to improve the performance of IP. To prove our algorithm, the OpenAI/Gym and Keras libraries are used to develop DQN. All results showed that our proposed controller has higher performance than the original DQN and could be applied to a nonlinear system.

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1. INTRODUCTION

An inverted pendulum (IP) system consists of a pendulum mounted on a cart pole. The goal is to maintain an angle between the pendulum and Y-axis by applying a force to the cart. This system is often considered a highly unstable system and difficult to control which becomes a classical problem in the control system domain.

In the last few years, many researchers have applied many well-known controllers such as proportional integral derivative (PID), linear quadratic regulator (LQR), sliding mode control (SMC), and fuzzy to achieve the stabilization control of the IP system. Herein, PID [1], [2] and LQR [3]–[5] are two popular controller methods that show great stabilization in many linear systems. The PID and LQR controller still have some disadvantages in controlling nonlinear systems like IP that need to be improved such as the settling time and overshoot percentage. Besides, SMC is a very powerful method in eliminating nonlinear systems. Many researchers [6]–[9] had presented the SMC for an IP system. Although the overshoot is decreased significantly, the control design is still complex and special to the chattering phenomenon problem. While fuzzy logic [10], LQR-PID [11], [12], and fuzzy-PID [13] have been considered to improve the performance of IP controllers. However, the equation computations are extremely complicated.

Besides the above traditional controller, some advanced controls are developed like adaptive control [14], [15] and robust control [16]. These results satisfied the basic requirement for the IP system, which gets higher performance than the traditional technique. But their design control and equation have still complex to apply to many different systems.

Nowadays, deep learning (DL) is the new method to make the controller more and more intelligent. The neural network (NN) could help the system to improve its self-learning in getting to the desired goal. For IP systems, many articles found out that robustness and effectiveness when using NN such as radial basis function (RBF) or multilayer feedforward neural network (MLFF NN) to control IP systems [17], [18]. Some researchers [19], [20] had also applied the fuzzy with neural networks but the networks are simple.

For the complexity of a non-linear and unstable, deep reinforcement learning (DRL) becomes well-known in building an intelligent system to solve very complicated problems based on its experiment in a specific environment, which had shown robustness [21]–[23] with different algorithms such as deep Q-networks (DQN), deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG), proximal policy optimization (PPO). Each algorithm has advantages and disadvantages for various situations. Besides, DRL is combined with the original control algorithm like PID-based DRL [24], reference signal self-organizing control system based DRL [25]. All presentations have given well results which could maintain the pendulum angle close to zero degrees. However, DQN for the inverse pendulum generates the force control for the cart with two values (two outputs from NN) the positive force and negative force [26], [27] related to two actions of DRL which is decided by a neural network. The changing force with a high range may make the oscillation of the cart effect. Therefore, this paper will develop a DQN algorithm for controlling the angle of the inverted pendulum system using a small range of force by many outputs from NN values to reduce oscillation based on the NN structure. Fully, the performance of IP is improved significantly. The algorithm results are presented based on the OpenAI/Gym and Keras libraries.

The paper is organized as: firstly, we are going to present the model configuration and the mathematic equation of the IP system in section 2. Secondly, we introduce the reinforcement learning method and DQN in section 3. Then, the performance of our proposal is presented and compared to the original methods in section 4. Finally, the conclusions are given in section 5.

2. METHOD

2.1. Inverse pendulum modeling

The model of an inverted pendulum is described in Figure 1. In general, the IP consists of a pendulum on the top of the cart while moving forward/backward along the rail and the pendulum can move freely around the joint between it and the cart. The dynamical equation of the IP system [28] can be presented as (1) and (2), where the parameters are defined in Table 1. To maintain the desired angle between the pendulum and Y-axis, the DRL is developed to generate F_a for the cart based on deep reinforcement learning, which is presented in the next section.

$$\ddot{\theta} = \frac{g_c(M+m)\sin\theta - (F_a + m l \dot{\theta}^2 \sin\theta)\cos\theta}{l\left(\frac{4}{3}(M+m) - m\theta\right)} \quad (1)$$

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{F_a + m l (\dot{\theta}^2 \sin\theta - \ddot{\theta} \cos\theta)}{M+m} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. IP modeling

Table 1. The parameters of inverse pendulum

Parameters	Meaning	Unit
M	Mass of cart	kg
m	Mass of pendulum	kg
θ	Angle of pendulum	$degree$
x	Position of Cart	m
l	Half of the length pendulum	m
F_a	Force to cart	N
g_c	Acceleration of gravity	m/s^2

2.2. Reinforcement learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) is a type of machine learning in which its concept is trial and error. Objects using RL can learn from their experience in an environment. A typical model using RL is described in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Reinforcement learning diagram

RL contains two main components: agent and environment. Herein, the environment uses the input action $a(t)$ from agent to generate a state $s(t)$ and reward $r(t)$ which are sent back to the agent. An algorithm is developed in the agent to find the best action based on the policy π which goal aims to achieve maximum reward in return. RL becomes a closed loop between the environment and the agent. Each loop is called a step. Let us define an episode containing N steps. The training process will be performed within $N \times M$ loop times where N is the number step and M is the number of episodes as below code example.

```

For i in range(M):           //Loop episode
  Reset state (s(t)) of environment to initial
  For j in range(N):       // Loop N steps
    // Send state (s(t)) to Agent
    // Using policy to generate action a(t)
    // Send action to Environment
    // Environment will create new states s(t+1)
    // Environment uses some conditions to create the reward r(t)
    // if ((theta>-12) and (theta<12)) reward+=1 else reward +=0; break;
    //Update policy based on state and action
  
```

Normally, RL uses the Epsilon-greedy method [29], [30] as the policy to generate the action. This policy can use a table named Q-table as the reference which shows the relationship between the state and the action. Each value in Q-table is called by Q-value $Q(s_j, a_i)$ where $j=(1, 2, \dots, m)$ and $i=(1, 2, \dots, n)$. For example, Q-table is shown in Table 2. And the selected action can be given by the policy as in (3). Where ε is the probability in selection random action, with a range from 0 to 1. The main purpose of RL is to find the maximum total reward based on policy. The updated policy is very important to select the best action for the environment, which can be applied [31] as Bellman equation in (4).

$$a_{(t)} = \begin{cases} a_i & \text{at } \max Q(s_i, a_j) & \text{with probability } (1 - \varepsilon) \\ a_r & \text{at Random action} & \text{with probability } \varepsilon \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$Q_{new}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)}) \leftarrow r_{(t+1)} + \gamma \max(Q(s_{(t+1)}, a_{(t+1)})) \quad (4)$$

where $Q_{new}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$ is the new Q-value at time t , γ is discount factor, range value from 0 to 1, $r_{(t+1)}$ is reward obtained with state $s_{(t+1)}$ at time $(t+1)$, $a_{(t+1)}$ is the action in time $(t+1)$, $\max(Q(s_{(t+1)}, a_{(t+1)}))$ is the maximum of Q-value target gets in the next state $s_{(t+1)}$ with action $a_{(t+1)}$ at the time $(t+1)$.

Table 2. Q-table of RL

	Action 1	Action 2	Action n
State 1	$Q(s_1, a_1)$	$Q(s_1, a_2)$...	$Q(s_1, a_n)$
State 2	$Q(s_2, a_1)$	$Q(s_2, a_2)$...	$Q(s_2, a_n)$
State
State m	$Q(s_m, a_1)$	$Q(s_m, a_2)$...	$Q(s_m, a_n)$

Based on the current state $s_{(t)}$, the agent has to generate the new action $a_{(t)}$ using the policy in (3) which will send to Environment to make the new state $s_{(t+1)}$ and new reward $r_{(t+1)}$. This state s_{t+1} is used to

find $\max(Q(s_{(t+1)}, a_{(t+1)}))$ in (4) among all Q-values $Q(s_{(t+1)}, a_i)$ which relates to actions a_i in Table 2 with $i=(1, 2, \dots, n)$. Therefore, the $Q_{new}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$ in (4) is computed and updated into Q-table on position $Q(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$.

Many applications require a lot of actions and states. The size of the Q-table will be extremely large and consume lots of time and resources in calculating Q-value. Therefore, DQN is one solution to overcome the limitations of the Q-table, which is presented in the next content.

2.3. Deep Q-network

Deep Q-networks (DQN) uses NN to approximate Q-value $Q(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$ instead of using the Q-table in the RL method. This NN will make one model named the prediction model (PM) which contains three layers that are the input layer (the current state of the environment), the hidden layer (computations with activation function), and the output layer (predict the Q-value). The DQN model is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. DQN model using a neural network

Instead of finding $\max(Q(s_{(t+1)}, a_{(t+1)}))$ in 4 from Table 1, another NN named the target model (TM) is used to estimate this value and then substitute it into 4 to computed $Q_{new_eq}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$: $Q_{new_eq}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)}) = r_{(t+1)} + \gamma \max(Q(s_{(t+1)}, a_{(t+1)}))$. On the other hand, TM has also defined the same architecture network with PM which is developed to estimate the $Q_{new_eq}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$ [21]. The error between $Q_{new_eq}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$ and $Q_{new_NN}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$ will be used to update the PM's weight using the gradient descent method. The loss function for updating can be defined as (5).

$$Loss = [Q_{new_eq}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)}) - Q_{new_NN}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})]^2 \quad (5)$$

To apply the training process, a set of training data need to be created. In the initial, a random state and reward are generated and sent to the agent (including PM and policy) as in Figure 4. Herein, the PM is used to predict the Q-values $Q_{new_NN}(s_{(t)j}, a_{(t)i})$ and use the policy in (3) to select the best action for the environment. Therefore, the environment will have a new state and reward to make a closed loop. Let us define N loop times, a set of training data in the form $E_{(t)} = (s_{(t)}, a_{(t)}, r_{(t+1)}, s_{(t+1)})$ is stored into experience replay (ER), which is applied in the training step as Figure 5. Next, let us define the inputs of TM and PM. One random sample $E_{(t)}$ in ER is selected for TM and PM with $s_{(t)}$ and $s_{(t+1)}$, respectively. Therefore, we can be given the output the $Q_{new_eq}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$ and $Q_{new_NN}(s_{(t)}, a_{(t)})$ for (5).

In this paper, we propose a modification of the DQN method by increasing the output of the neural network model. It makes the IP system more and more stable and easy to reach an upright position ($\theta = 0$). To demonstrate this, we create the IP environment based on OpenAI/Gym which is open-source and apply the DQN algorithm with different number outputs for the agent part in RL to control IP maintenance with an angle. The simulation and result will be performed and discussed in the next section.

Figure 4. RL using the DQN method

Figure 5. Training DQN process

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, our proposal is performed to demonstrate the performance of IP. Firstly, let us define the parameters of IP as in Table 3. Secondly, from (1), the output states of environment are defined as four parameters: $[x, \dot{x}, \theta, \dot{\theta}]$. Where \dot{x} is the linear velocity of the cart (m/s) along the rail and the $\dot{\theta}$ is the angular velocity (rad/s). Next, we define the condition to decide the reward as in (6). Thirdly, the agent will generate the action, which is presented by the neural network. Three cases with different numbers of output nodes are shown in Table 4, which contain 2, 3, and 17 outputs from the neural network.

$$reward = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } -12 < \theta < 12 \\ 0 & \text{if } \theta < -12 \text{ or } \theta > 12 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Table 3. The special parameters of the inverse pendulum

Parameters	Values
M	1.0
m	0.1
l	0.5
F_a	8.0
g_c	9.8

Table 4. Neural network configuration in three cases

Name	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3 (our proposal)
Number of inputs	4	4	4
Number of hidden layers	4	4	4
Number of the node in each hidden layer	18	18	18
Number of outputs	2	3	17
Training steps	70,000	70,000	70,000

Fourthly, each model will be trained in 70,000 steps. In the training step, the cart-pole system will be terminated if its angle is greater than 12 degrees or less than -12 degrees. Figure 6 shows the total reward value obtained from each episode while training three models in 70,000 steps. Herein, Figures 6(a) to 6(c) present for each case of model 1, model 2, and model 3, respectively which are described in Table 4. For clearly, we computed the average reward in the last 50 episodes (blue line). Because the DQN model learns based on the trial-and-error process, so the total reward could change based on ratio error and success in the trial process. All steps are performed on a computer with the specification as CPU (Intel Core i7-7500U 2.7 GHz (4CPUs)), GPU (NVIDIA GEFORCE MX150, 2 GB), RAM (12 GB), HDD (256 GB).

Next, the testing step will use the NN which is trained in the previous step. Herein, the weight of NN is often updated for each training step. All models are tested during 400 steps with the initial angle of the pendulum at 17 degrees and the desired angle is 0 degrees.

As the results in Figures 7(a) and 7(b), the forces in model 1 and model 2 are only selected by $(-F_a, F_a)$ and $(-F_a, 0, F_a)$, respectively. Because the force applied to the cart-pole in each step is very high (either $-F_a/F_a$ and $-F_a/0/F_a$) which affects the cart pole by some oscillation as in Figure 7(c). It means that the performance of IP is weakened. Model 3 makes the force-like continuously $(-F_a, -F_a+1, -F_a+2, \dots, 0, 1, 2, \dots, F_a)$ corresponded to 17 outputs of NN, which could reduce oscillation for the cart pole and the system has higher performance than model 1 and model 2. Furthermore, model 3 has a lower overshoot and quickly makes a stable system than other models as in Figure 8. The cart pole could maintain desired angle (0 degrees) of the pendulum.

Figure 6. Reward and average reward in 50 episodes gained with the training 70,000 steps (a) reward and average reward of model 1, (b) reward and average reward of model 2, and (c) reward and average reward of model 3

Figure 7. Force tracking in each model (a) force control in model 1, (b) force control in model 2, and (c) force control in model 3

Figure 8. Response angle in each model

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the method for controlling the inverted pendulum based on DQN in DRL. By creating a different number of outputs of NN in DQN, our proposal used 17 outputs that have higher performance than the original DQN method using two and three outputs. All results showed that the angle of IP reaches the desired value with zeros degree very fast and more stable. This proposed controller could provide well performance for nonlinear systems of IP and other systems. In the future, a real system of the inverse pendulum will be developed and applied DQN for controlling the angle of the pendulum as well as the position of the cart.

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